

Energy Efficient Routing Protocols for Node Distribution in Wireless Sensor Networks

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ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor networks comprise of sensor nodes that have constrained preparing ability, little memory and low energy source. These nodes are sent haphazardly and frequently thickly in nature. In observing applications, sensor nodes sense information from nature intermittently and after that transmit them to a base station which is called sink node. In this way information transmission expends node's energy taking into account transmission separation. In many wireless sensors arranges, the energy wellspring of the node is constrained and can't be minimized. Here, we have proposed the Efficient Energy based Multipath Cluster Routing Protocol for minimizing the energy utilization in WSNs. In multipath routing, system is composed as a gathering of networks. It gives burden adjusting and expanded throughput to the system. As per information transmission component of WSN, we evaluate the forward transmission zone, characterize forward energy thickness which constitutes forward-mindful variable with connection weight. For energy effective transmission in occasion driven WSN, information ought to be decreased. It obliges legitimate directing strategy for solid transmission of collected information to sink from the source nodes. Propose another correspondence convention in light of forward-mindful calculate request to focus next-bounce node and IEAR directing calculation is to decrease the quantity of transmissions and therefore adjusting the energy utilization, drawing out the system capacity lifetime and to enhance QoS of WSN.

Keywords: *Wireless sensor networks, Routing protocols, energy-efficient protocol, Wireless Sensor Networks*

I. Introduction

A Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) A colossal number of nodes are utilized to make a sensor system and these nodes are organized thickly to one another to screen them. The information is gathered by the every node and transmits that data back to the sink. WSN goes under Low Range Wireless Personal Area Network (LRWPAN) packet. These nodes comprise of CPU, memory, battery and handset. The span of every sensor node may fluctuate taking into account the applications. The system ought to have the self-sorting out ability on the grounds that the positions of individual nodes are not known at first. Participation among the nodes is the fundamental component of this system. The gathering of nodes collaborates to circulate the assembled data to their neighbor clients in this system. The critical application zones of the sensor networks are the military ranges, characteristic calamity and in wellbeing. Moreover, this system is utilized to screen the light, temperature, moistness and other ecological elements for the common applications. B. Energy Balancing in WSN Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are introduced and conveyed to do distinctive applications, for example, Environmental Monitoring, Targeting, Industrial Control, Disaster Recovery, Nuclear, Biological & Chemical assault Detection

Reconnaissance and Battlefield Surveillance. This Wireless Sensor Networks are required to assume more vital part later on era networks to sense the physical world [1,2,3,4,7]. It is extremely surely understood that the energy is the most genuine and discriminating asset for battery-fueled Sensor Networks. To amplify the lifetime of this system as far as might be feasible, the energy effectiveness turns into the most essential parameter amid the Protocol plan. With a specific end goal to accomplish and utilize the constrained energy at sensor nodes successfully, the as of late proposed directing plans are endeavoring to locate the base energy way to the sink, which is utilized to streamline the energy use at nodes. From the writing study, be that as it may, it is watched that to concentrate on the productivity of energy while outlining conventions for WSNs is not adequate. Furthermore distinguished that the uneven energy exhaustion which is drastically diminishes the lifetime of networks and reductions the sensors scope proportion. Also, Furthermore, these outcomes in [4] point out that one bounce far from the sink will deplete their energy level, there still up to ninety three percent of beginning energy left at these nodes past away. Also, this awkwardness of energy utilization unevenness is absolutely undesirable for the long haul quality and strength of the sensor system. These sensor nodes itself expend their energy heavier equally, then the network between these sensors and the sink could be kept up for a more drawn out time and in this manner the system packet may be deferred. This wonderful debasement of the system integration could be clearly given generous increases. What's more, subsequently, it ought to be sane to make a suitable exchange off between both the energy productivity and the adjusted energy utilization. It considers the offset directing of energy conveyance. In view of the definite investigation of the information transmission instrument of WSN, I evaluate the forward transmission range, characterize forward energy thickness, which constitutes forward-mindful component with connection weight, and propose another energy equalization directing convention in light of forward-mindful variable (FAF-EBRM). Hence adjusts the energy utilization, drags out the capacity lifetime. Organizing unattended sensor nodes are required to have noteworthy effect on the effectiveness of numerous military and common applications, for example, battle field reconnaissance, security and calamity administration. These frameworks process information accumulated from different sensors to screen occasions in a territory of hobby. Case in point, in a calamity administration setup, countless can be dropped by a helicopter. Organizing these sensors can

help salvage operations by finding survivors, recognizing dangerous territories and making the salvage group more mindful of the general circumstance. Such use of sensor networks not just can build the productivity of salvage operations additionally guarantee the security of the salvage group.

II. Related Work

In this paper [1], a dynamic packet directing calculation for WSN was introduced. It is involved three stages including packet head (CH) determination, group setup and between packet routing. Packet heads are chosen in light of remaining energy and node load. At that point the non-Cluster head nodes pick a group by contrasting the expense capacity of its neighbor CHs. Group heads corresponds with base state utilizing multi-jump correspondence. In this paper [2], half breed QEA-based energy effective directing calculation (HERA) was proposed which is taking into account LEACH and PEGASIS calculations in the earth of wireless sensor networks. To lessen the transmission separate, the calculation utilizes the crossover quantum developmental calculation (HQEA) to set up the best clusterbased multi-chain topology. To adjust the energy dissemination, node's remaining energy and its separation from the objective are considered. In this paper [3], burden equalization routing calculation was proposed taking into account uneven grouping to do uneven packeting and figure ideal number of grouping. It keeps the quantity of normal node under some certain packet head from being too extensive which leads burden to be overweight to death through even nodepacketing. It builds assessment capacity which can better reflect remaining energy conveyance of nodes and in the meantime develops routing assessment capacity between group heads. In this paper [4], single-bounce sending plan was proposed and demonstrated to expend less energy than multi-jump sending plan inside of the correspondence scope of the source sensor or a current forwarder, utilizing free space energy utilization model. It was received that the social welfare capacity to foresee imbalance of lingering energy of neighbors in the wake of selecting diverse next bounce nodes. In light of energy imbalance, the technique is intended to process the level of energy parity.

Directing to accomplish lifetime changes by burden adjusting and abusing cross-layer data in wireless sensor system. The packet based wireless sensor system (WSN) can improve the entire system lifetime. In every group, the packet head (CH) assumes a critical part in totaling and sending information detected by other

regular nodes. Fluffy rationale plan is utilized as a part of this calculation.

III. Routing Protocols in Wsn

A wireless sensor networks[1] is a self-organization wireless network system consist of sensors nodes with limited energy. They are used to monitor the sensing field and collect information from physical or environmental condition and to cooperatively pass the collected data through the network to a main location [12]. Due to the limited energy and communication ability of sensor nodes, it is important to design a network topology, routing algorithm and protocol for large-scale wsn communication system. energy consumption is an important factor in system designs of WSNs. Traditionally, there are two approaches to accomplish the data collection task: direct communication, and multihop forwarding. in one hop wireless communication, the sensor nodes upload data directly to the sink, which may result in long communication distances and degrade the energy efficiency of sensor nodes. on the other hand, in multihop[4] forwarding, data are transferred from the nodes to the sink through multiple relays, and thus communication distance is reduced[7]. however, since nodes closer to the sink have a much heavier forwarding load, their energy may be depleted rapidly, which degrades the network performance.

A. ENERGY EFFICIENT CLUSTERING PROTOCOLS

Katiyar et al. [4] surveyed clustering algorithms for wireless sensor networks. They classified clustering algorithms based on two main criterions: according to the stability and energy efficiency. They also surveyed several energy-efficient clustering protocols for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. In this section, we want to survey and compare other energy efficient protocols for clustering in wireless sensor networks.

B. ENERGY EFFICIENT HETEROGENEOUS CLUSTERED SCHEME

Dilipand and Patel [5] proposed an energy efficient heterogeneous clustered scheme (EEHC), for electing cluster heads in a distributed fashion in hierarchical wireless sensor networks. The election probabilities of cluster heads are weighted by the residual energy of a node relative to that of other nodes in the network. The algorithm is based on LEACH and works on the election processes of the cluster head in presence of

heterogeneity of nodes. Simulations results show that EEHC is more effective in prolonging the network lifetime compared with LEACH.

C. DISTRIBUTED ENERGY BALANCE

CLUSTERING PROTOCOL ChangminDuan and Hong Fan [7] proposed a distributed energy balance clustering (DEBC) protocol for wireless sensor networks. Cluster heads are selected by a probability depending on the ratio between remaining energy of node and the average energy of network. The high initial and remaining energy nodes have more chances to be the cluster heads than the low energy nodes. This protocol also considers two-level heterogeneity and then it extends the results for multi-level heterogeneity. DEBC is different from LEACH, which make sure each node can be cluster head in each $n_i=1/p$ rounds. Simulation results show that the performance of DEBC is better than LEACH and SEP.

D. WEIGHTED ELECTION PROTOCOL

Rashed et al. [1] proposed an energy-efficient routing protocol in order to enhance the stability period of wireless sensor networks. This protocol is called weighted election protocol (WEP). It introduces a scheme to combine clustering strategy with chain routing algorithm for satisfy both energy and stable period constrains under heterogeneous environment in wireless sensor networks. In the scheme, the authors have considered the following assumptions:

Each sensor node has power control and the ability to transmit data to any other sensor node or directly to the base station.

In the model, two types of nodes are used such as advanced node and normal node where advanced nodes have more energy than normal ones.

IV. Proposed work

Propose Methodology of Forward Aware Protocol will design in to three model such as Network model, Establishment of the Model and Design of the FAF-EBRM.

Network Model

All sensor nodes are isomorphic, and they have limited capabilities to compute, communicate and store data. The set of sensor nodes is defined as and is the total number of nodes. Here, is the identifier for a node. The energy of sensor nodes is limited, and the initial energy

is stored. Nodes die after exhausting energy entirely. However, the energy of the sink node can be added. Locations of nodes and Sink do not change after being fixed, and a node cannot obtain the absolute position depend on its own location device. Nodes can vary transmission power according to the distance to its receiver. The sink node can broadcast message to all sensor nodes in the sensing field. The distance between the signal source and receiver can be computed based on the received signal strength. Regional central nodes are not selected at the beginning, on the contrary, they spring up during the topology evolution. Importance nodes have more connections, whose degree and intensity are significantly higher than neighbor nodes.

Establishment of the Model

In WSN clustered hierarchical routing protocols, sometimes nodes of a cluster are closer to the sink than the cluster head is, but it should transmit data to the head node, If this backward transmission is frequent.

Design of FAF-EBRM

A topology reconnecting mechanism of the cluster head rotation algorithm like LEACH is needed. The whole WSN information is limited, and global topology change may affect the information perception, the global change caused by energy unbalanced area is a waste of energy to energy balanced area, so a local topology reconfiguration mechanism is necessary. It is an actual design factor.

V. Topology Control

For understanding topology control first of all we have to know what is the meaning of the topology. The connectivity of the wireless network and the application of routing protocols to network are considered as topology. Topology influences important features of the network like resiliency and communication cost between nodes. Current research has established efficient network energy utilization as one of the fundamental research issues in wireless sensor networks. Controlling the topology of the network has emerged as an effective solution to the above problem. Like all other aspects of wireless sensor networks, topology control protocols have to be designed and implemented subject to a severe set of computational energy constraints. The radio in a sensor node is the primary source of energy dissipation. The radio consumes power in all of its four phases of operation namely listening, idle, transmission and reception. Some common metrics that are used for performance measurement of routing protocols in wireless adhoc

networks are number of packets dropped, overhead in terms of routing messages, number of hops etc. But, compared to traditional wired and wireless adhoc networks, wireless sensor networks should be primarily evaluated in terms of energy depletion of sensor nodes. Sensor nodes have limited battery sources, moreover once deployed there is seldom any means of recharging the battery of a sensor node in a hostile environment. These limitations make the above stated energy metric a primary concern. Choosing the approach to selectively switching off the radio of sensor nodes based on the availability of alternate routing paths is one way of optimizing the energy consumption in a wireless sensor network. Switching off the radio of the sensor nodes is only possible if the topology is configured in such a way that the network is not partitioned due to those inactive nodes. Thus effectively controlling the topology of the network emerges as a solution to the problem of energy conservation for wireless sensor networks. Topology control protocols are designed to exploit node density in the network to extend the network lifetime and provide connectivity. The following criteria have been identified as the key concepts for designing topology control protocols for wireless sensor networks. To reduce the energy dissipated in the network topology control protocols should take advantage of the high node density in large-scale wireless sensor networks to reduce the energy dissipated in the network. To accommodate changing network dynamics sensor nodes should be able to self-configure. Redundant nodes should be selected based on distributed localized algorithms. Topology control protocols must possess minimum connectivity in the network, so that the network is not partitioned.

VI. Simulation results

The simulation results have been obtained using the quantitative analysis. NS-2 has been used to simulate the results. The energy consumption IEAR routing protocol designed is being compared and the results are shown.

Fig. Energy Consumption

Fig. Packet Delivery Ratio

Fig. Throughput

Fig. Overhead: Packets vs Number of Events

In the experiment, we evaluate the performance of the routing protocols as the area of the sensor field is increased. IEAR is organized into rounds, where each

of them begins with a set-up phase, and is followed by data transfer [8] phase. Usually, the latter phase is longer than the former phase. Their sub-phases include advertisement, cluster set-up, schedule creation, and data transmission phases. In advertisement phase, the self-selected cluster-heads [1] broadcast advertisement messages in their clusters, and the non-cluster-head nodes decide which clusters they belong to based on the received signal strength. In data transmission phase, each node waits for its turn to send data if needed. IEAR protocol provides sensor networks with many good features, such as clustering architecture, localized coordination and randomized rotation of cluster-heads. In data transmission phase, each node waits for its turn to send data if needed.

VII. Conclusion

In this paper, we have developed a cluster based multipath routing protocol which attains multipath routing, multipath construction and energy consumption model to make a correct balance between network life time, energy consumption and end to end delay in the sensor nodes. In the first phase of the scheme, clustering scheme is proposed to select cluster head. In second phase, construction of multipath routing tree is implemented. In third phase, energy consumption model and average energy consumption can be minimized based on the condition of average packet delivery rate. It is demonstrated that energy consumption of each node. By simulation results we have shown that the EEMCRP achieves good throughput, high network lifetime, low energy consumption, good delivery ratio while attaining low delay, energy consumption than the existing schemes FAF-EBRP while varying the number of nodes, simulation time, throughput and pause time.

This research work was motivated for data aggregation in fixed-power WSNs. Routes are managed based on expected path length and a weighted combination of distance travelled, energy level and RF link performance history.

Simulation results have shown that it performs competitively against existing routing protocols in terms of packet delivery ratio, packet latency, scalability, and energy consumption while operating in a noisy wireless environment where network traffic, link disruptions and node failure rates are high. Future work includes studying the open issues and investigating the security aspects of EAR, especially in clustered WSNs.

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